

The Analysis of Palestine Conflict and UN Role

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ABSTRACT: The world is shifting the paradigm of resolving conflicts. The countries are actively participating in resolving the issue and conflict prevailing globally. The platform of UN is considered among the main medium to resolve conflicts internationally. This article is in depth overview of past, present and future perspective of one of the long-existing conflicts of the world. The Palestine conflict is a matter of serious concern for East and West. There is a critical point arises that the Palestine-Israel conflict is a “three-fold test” for the world peace. The conflict till present has gone through many shifts from war to UN resolutions. This conflict is a question mark on the conflict resolution ability of UN. This article argues the test capacity of UN to bring both Palestine and Israel to an accord. The UN’s handling of the matter would have consequences for the organizations standing in the world.

KEYWORDS: Conflict, Palestine, Israel, UN, Resolution

Historical Overview of the Conflict

Background to the establishment of the Jewish state

The idea of the establishment of a Jewish state has been gaining ground among Jews over the centuries, and this idea has been particularly strengthened by four elements:

The specific conspiratorial temperament of the Jews

The specific conspiratorial temperament of the Jews is well-known. They cannot coexist in any society, and one of the main goals of establishing the well-known enlightened movement 'Haskala' was that they, contrary to this, create a spirit of coexistence in the society. However, this movement failed completely. Since the failure of this movement, such ideas were rapidly emerging among them that they have to form a separate state, where they can live in peace and contentment (Ayapbergen et al. 2020).

Modern National Ideology

Protestantism began to take root in Europe in the last centuries, especially in the nineteenth century, when governments based on national ideologies started to emerge, and Christian states began to strengthen. Since he had been using the slogan since the sixteenth century, he too seized the opportunity and, with great planning, began to make the idea a reality. Later, in 1897, the Zionist movement was launched for this purpose. This movement led to a very strong and very planned movement for the establishment of an Israeli state in Palestine on a global scale (Chomsky & Pappé 2015).

The conspiracy of the Western world

An important thing was also the conspiracy of the Western world’s conspiracy. The Western world was well aware of their conspiratorial temperament and their rhetoric against the governments, so it did not form a separate Jewish state. He not only paved the way, but also openly accepted the patronage of this state. The West thought that in this way, on the one hand, it would get rid of their actions, and on the other hand, it would be able to close the chapter of their ancient enmity with the Christian world by colliding with the Muslim world (Gil 1997).

Oppression of the Jewish Nation

Because of the Jews' own temperament and actions, no government could tolerate them for long. Their history shows that because of their temperament, they could be more peaceful anywhere. Not long after, Russia and other countries inflicted a lot of atrocities on them, and then the Holocaust drama not only made their oppression better known, but also the establishment of a separate Jewish state on a global scale. The way was also paved for (Chomsky & Pappé 2015).

Why chooses Palestine?

The Jews had more than one option for establishing the state of Israel, but they chose Palestine for it, and the United Kingdom gave its full support and all possible assistance. While it has a religious foundation, the construction of the Temple of Solomon according to religious teachings, there have been some dangerous political conspiracies in the Western world behind it. The West knows that if the Jews succeed in fulfilling their dream of a greater Israel, they can play a dangerous role in the politics of the Muslim world, where there will be a gap between African and Asian Muslim countries (Chomsky & Pappé 2015).

At the same time, they will continue to make the entire region a victim of their conspiracies. The fact is that since the establishment of the state of Israel, the entire Muslim world has been plagued by strange disturbances and troubles. It is a detailed topic of the dangerous effects of the establishment of the Jewish state on the politics of the Middle East or the Muslim world, but the fact remains that the state of Israel is currently playing a dangerous and influential role in the politics of the Muslim world (Gil 1997). Whether it is the overthrow of Egypt's elected democracy, the accusations of terrorism against the great Islamic movements of the Islamic world, and the mass arrests of their activists. The obstacles to the establishment of democratic and independent governments in the Islamic world. Whether it's the problem of keeping the governments of the Islamic world economically dependent on others, Israel is playing a significant role. According to Dr. Mohsen Saleh, "The situation now is that in order to strengthen Israel, it is necessary to weaken the surrounding Muslim countries, and the condition for the strength, awakening and unity of the Islamic world is that the world through Israel The Zionist plan imposed on Islam should be weakened." (Proofs and facts in the case of Palestine).

Some consider the issue of Palestine to be a religious issue for the Jews. Of course, there is a religious dimension to it. Yes, and it is based on an anti-Islamic political agenda, in which the Western world is using the Jews as a mere card (Chomsky & Pappé 2015).

The beginning of the Zionist movement and the role of the West

Zionist state

The ideology of the Zionist state came to the process during the First World War, because Britain needed Jewish capital to pay for the war. While the Jews wanted to form a separate state, the British did not want to offend the Arabs. Therefore, in the "Bosphorus Declaration" he assured the creation of a homeland for the Jews but did not clarify its nature. The land of Palestine was chosen for this Jewish kingdom (Glueck 1933).

The most in compassionate or compel circumstances are for the Palestinians who are occupied in-between Gaza and west Bank Strip or are outcast in camps across the area. The critical circumstance reveals the need of discovering useful strides for modifying fundamental resources of human regarding the Palestinian people (Gill 1997). During World War II, the map of this state became prominent and Jews from all over the world began to turn to Palestine. Their rapid arrival in Palestine will upset the Arabs and they strongly opposed it. But the influx of Jews continued because they had the support of Britain and the United States. However, when World

War II broke out in 1939, Jewish settlements were restricted to appease the Arabs. At that time, the Jewish-Arab population in Palestine was 3 to 10 percent (Gregory 2004).

In 1945, the Arabs planned to form the Arab League to end this new tribulation. During this time, an Anglo-American committee was set up to make recommendations on the future of Palestine. Since this was part of a plan to establish a Jewish state in Palestine, the Arabs boycott it. But after the war, a significant number of Jews had settled in Palestine. And Britain realized that now that it had withdrawn its troops from Palestine, the Jews could establish their own independent state. Therefore, he declared Palestine a failure to find a solution to the problem and handed over Palestine to the United Nations (Gil 1997).

While that law has never kept any state from keeping up its essential security rights during emergency, it gives a base restricting lawful structure as well as a space for suspecting and connecting basically on the human outcomes of security strategies (Karsh 2010). There were riots against the Jews from 1929 to 1933, but the British troops severely crushed these riots. Hitler's anti-Semitism led to a new wave of Jewish arrivals in Palestine, and in 1935 alone, 60,000 Jews arrived (Gil 1997).

During World War II, the Zionists cooperated with the British government and provided financial support to the Allies (Karsh 2010).

United Nation

After the war, the British presented the issue of Palestine to the United Nations on April 2, 1947. On May 15, a special UN committee was set up, which unanimously agreed that the British occupation of Palestine should end. The committee members could not agree on a future government. The majority proposed the establishment of an Arab government in the area below Central Palestine. The territories of Jerusalem and Bethlehem should be handed over to the United Nations and a Jewish state should be established in the area above these cities up to the Mediterranean (McCarthy 1990).

On November 29, 1947, the UN General Assembly adopted a proposal by a majority of the committee members. The assembly also set up a five-member commission to implement the plan. The commission was tasked with assisting in the formation of an interim government in consultation with Jewish and Arab groups.

Almost every component of Israel's control of the Palestinian Territories disregards an arrangement of the Fourth Geneva Convention. A significant number of Israel's infringement are grave breaks of the Convention and are considered 'Atrocities' under International Law (Pappe 2004). The Arabs rejected the UN plan, saying that establishing a Jewish state in the Arab region was offensive and resisted. The United Kingdom also announced that the plan would not be implemented by force. And the British government will take over the administration on May 15, 1948, ending the occupation. This period of about 6 months in Palestine was the time of confrontations. Guerrilla warfare between Arabs and Jews had begun. The UN commission had not even begun implementing the partition plan.

The last High Commissioner of Palestine, Sir Gordon, left Palestine on May 14, 1948, in the midst of chaos. And at 4 pm on the same day, Ben-Gurion unilaterally announced the establishment of the Jewish state of Israel at a meeting of the National Council of Jews and the General Zionist Council in Tel Aviv. David Ben-Gurion was appointed the first Prime Minister of the Provisional Government of Israel, and on May 16, 1948, the United States and, just a day later, Russia recognized the Jewish state (Quigley 2005).

Egypt, Jordan, Iraq, Syria and Lebanon invaded Israel to end the Jewish occupation of Palestine. Western powers were behind Israel, so the Arabs had to accept a ceasefire after eight months of fierce fighting. But he refused to acknowledge the existence of Israel. Count Bernardert, the UN mediator for Palestine, was killed by Jewish terrorists in Jerusalem during the eight-month war (Gil 1997). He was replaced by Ralph Beach, who could barely contain the fighting. However, the Jews managed to occupy much more territory (Said 1992).

The position of the United Nations

Britain's breach of this treaty led to a catastrophic event in November 1947, when the UN General Council, in its 181st resolution, divided Palestine into Arab and Jewish. There was so much open rigging that 54% of the country's territory was earmarked for the Jewish state, and only 45% for the Arab state, while the 1% for Quds was considered an international area (Gil 1997).

According to Dr. Mohsin Saleh, "This was not a mandatory decision in accordance with the principles of the United Nations itself, and secondly, this decision was in conflict with the principles of the United Nations. The basis of the United Nations is that freedom belongs to every country and every nation." It is a fundamental right, and the country and its people will decide this freedom. In addition, a major mistake was that the Palestinian people, who were a key part of the issue, were not consulted before the decision was made, nor was a referendum held in the country. They were later resettled here and given an important and large part of the land (Smith 2004, 320).

A Constant Conflict

Although the United Nations arranged a cease-fire between Israel and Arab countries in 1948, the region remained insecure. In anticipation for future confrontation, both sides increased their military capabilities. Meanwhile, many Palestinians have joined resistance organizations, outraged by the refugee crisis and their political and economic situation. A number of these organizations combined in 1964 to become the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO), which was quickly led by Yasser Arafat. Over the following three decades, Israel and its Arab neighbors went to war three times: in 1956, 1967, and 1973 (Glueck 1933).

The Sinai Peninsula, the Golan Heights, Gaza, the West Bank, and East Jerusalem were all captured and occupied by Israel during the 1967 Six-Day War. This occupation, which has lasted till now, is not permanent, according to international law. Not only was Israel several times larger than it had been in 1948, but it had also absorbed one million Palestinians. Furthermore, nearly 200,000 Palestinians were forced to flee their homes (mostly going to Jordan). Menachem Begin, the Israeli prime minister, began a push to construct Jewish colonies in the seized areas in 1977 (Gil1997).

Large numbers of Jewish settlers have flocked to East Jerusalem

The West Bank, and Gaza, even though the settlement strategy is divisive among Israelis and is illegal under international law. Palestinians have lost more land because of the settlements. Furthermore, the settlements have exacerbated conflict by creating armed settlers and Israeli forces within the occupied areas, as well as severely restricting Palestinian freedom of movement (as Israeli-only access routes and containment walls/checkpoints built to safeguard the settlements obstruct Palestinian movement). Often, Palestinian citizens are the victims of settler aggression, and Palestinian guerillas have retaliated by killing Israeli civilians (Gregory, 2004).

The war moved to Lebanon, where the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO) and the Israeli army both participated in the Lebanese Civil War. A vicious loop ensued: Israelis hampered Palestinians' political, economic, and travel capabilities, claiming security concerns, while Palestinians, outraged by Israeli treatment, expanded their resistance operations. The US sought to launch peace talks on a number of occasions, but its proclivity to sympathize with Israeli concerns hampered their efficacy (Gil 1997).

The Palestinians were in open revolt by late 1987, a spontaneous uprising that became known as the first "intifada" (Arabic for "resistance" or "shaking off"). Hundreds of thousands of Palestinians, especially teenagers, took part in civil disobedience (refusal to pay taxes, boycotts, and strikes) as well as throwing rocks at Israeli soldiers. Over 1,000 Palestinians were killed by the Israeli army, including hundreds of children under the age of 16. Israel's treatment of Palestinian civilians drew widespread condemnation both at home and internationally (Imseis 2020).

Similarly, Palestinian bombing assaults against Israeli citizens have persisted. Peace talks (see below) have taken place as a result of the suffering on both sides, but they have yielded only limited progress. Tensions and violence are still present today (Gil 1997).

Dividing Israelis and Palestinians on Important Issues

Security

Both sides are concerned about random attacks and acts of terrorism. Israelis dislike the fact that they can't stroll down the street without fear of anything – or someone – exploding next to them. Palestinians are angry that Israeli troops regularly abuse them, or that their homes and belongings are destroyed if a member of their family is suspected of attacking Israel — or if Israel wants the land for colonies, roads, or containment walls. Israelis argue that having soldiers on the ground and employing severe methods is vital to keep their citizens safe; Palestinians argue that such actions are what motivate them to attack Israel (Chomsky & Pappé 2015).

The Palestinians' main concerns

Since they believe that all refugees and their ancestors should have the right to return to their homeland. Many of them have spent decades (some even more than 60 years!) in refugee camps with deplorable living conditions. The challenge for Israelis is that there are now 4 million descendants of the original refugees due to a high Palestinian birthrate (Gil 1997).

Jerusalem control

Jews (original religious center), Christians (place of Jesus' ministry and crucifixion), and Muslims all revere this city (site from which the Prophet Muhammad is believed to have ascended into heaven). The issue is who should be in charge of it, and how should that power be distributed?

Israeli forces are located on Palestinian territory

Israelis claim that their forces are needed to maintain security; Palestinians claim that Israeli forces harass or even assault civilians. Palestinians want their own military to be in command of their own territory. For Israelis, the question is whether Palestinian forces can manage their own radical elements (Gil 1997).

Settlements by Israel on Palestinian territory

Thousands of Jewish settlers have poured into the Gaza Strip and the West Bank since the 1967 conflict, arguing that Israel has a Biblical right to the area. Palestinians despise settlers for annexing Palestinian territory, inciting violence against Palestinians, and prompting the deployment of Israeli military as well as the construction of walls and checkpoints. Many moderate Israelis agree, seeing the settlements as a roadblock to peace, but they confront a huge task in closing the settlements without sparking hostility from the local Jewish population (Chomsky, & Pappé 2015).

Humans and commodities movement in the Gaza and the West bank: Checkpoints, barriers, special highways, and other limitations on the mobility of Arab residents are necessary for Israeli security, according to Israelis. Such limitations, on the other hand, significantly harm the Palestinian economy by restricting trade and job prospects, as well as making it impossible for farmers to access their fields.

Palestinians' access to health care, schooling, and family/friends in other cities is likewise restricted. The peace process would have to strike a compromise between Israel's security needs and the Palestinians' desire for greater independence and economic prosperity (Irfan 2020).

The water element

Water is in short supply in the area, and Israel controls it both within Israel and in the Occupied Palestinian Territories. Palestinians are angry that Israeli settlements in the West Bank are permitted to consume six times the quantity of water that Palestinians are permitted to use. Environmentalists are concerned that the Dead Sea's environment may be jeopardized by water diversion (Irfan 2020).

Hateful propaganda and language

Both Palestinians and Jews are divided between moderates and radicals, with both seeing the other as less than human. On the surface, the issue of words appears to be less urgent than that of hostile armies, suicide bombers, or refugees. In truth, fanatics on both sides foment underlying fear and hostility, making it harder to create the mutual respect required for compromise (Imseis 2020).

The Peace Efforts

There have been attempts to reach a peaceful resolution as the violence took a toll on both sides. Israeli Prime Minister Menachem Begin and Egyptian President Anwar Sadat signed a peace accord in September 1978 during a summit at Camp David hosted by American President Jimmy Carter, which resulted in Israel's departure from Sinai. Even though Israel and Egypt had begun discussions, internal Israeli disputes were growing.

Only in 1991 did direct discussions between Palestinian and Israeli authorities begin. A series of discussions between the Israeli government, individual Arab governments, and the PLO were held in Madrid, Spain, under the pressure of the US and the Soviet Union. Some Israeli and Palestinian officials, on the other hand, wanted a less visible and highly heated setting and met in private in Norway (Imseis 2020).

Oslo Accords

In 1993, Israeli Prime Minister Yitzhak Rabin and Palestinian Authority Chairman Yasser Arafat signed the Oslo Accords. According to the Oslo Accords, Israel would withdraw its soldiers from Gaza and the West Bank town of Jericho, while the Palestinians would be given more authority. Palestinians will be able to elect a Self-Government Authority in these territories in the future. In exchange, the PLO decided to recognize Israel, a step that Israelis considered crucial to their security. Under Arafat's leadership, the Palestinian Authority was founded in 1994, and Jordan had joined Egypt in recognizing Israel (Pappe 2004).

Many of the important issues that now separate the two peoples were not addressed in the Oslo Accords, according to critics. Unfortunately, these concerns were never resolved, and both parties broke their agreements. In response to Israel's expanded settlements on Palestinian land, Palestinians upped their attacks against settlers. Extremism on both sides contributed to the conflict's subsequent escalation. In early 1994, an Israeli terrorist killed 30 Muslim worshippers in a mosque in Hebron, prompting a wave of suicide attacks by Palestinian terrorists (Quigley 2005).

The peace effort was immediately derailed. The hardship of both parties prompted more attempts at dialogue in 2000. Ehud Barak, the Israeli prime minister, and Yasser Arafat, the Palestinian leader, met in Camp David to try to find a settlement to the war. However, it quickly became clear that the underlying concerns that divide the two peoples are impossible to reconcile (Said 1992).

The peace process remains deadlocked to this day since no formal agreement was achieved. The last ten years have brought with them a new level of uncertainty. Yasser Arafat died in November 2004, and the more militant Hamas group was elected to senior posts in the Palestinian Authority little over a year later (in January 2006).

Israel has also adopted a more belligerent stance: an Israeli invasion of Lebanon in summer 2006, as well as assault on Palestinians there, drew international condemnation. In addition, Israeli colonization of the West Bank and East Jerusalem has grown, resulting in the confiscation of Palestinian land for settlements, the construction of barriers and restricted-access highways, and the seizure of water and other resources. Gaza became a focal point of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict between 2008 and 2012, resulting in Israeli assault on the territory and Palestinian assaults on Israeli people.

Unemployment is at an all-time high in Gaza, and the standard of life has plunged. On and off the conflict and breach of law has been gone through since the previous years, which was been observed by the international community (Karsh 2010).

Recent clash

Protests and rioting, police riot control, rocket launches on Israel by Hamas and Palestinian Islamic Jihad, and Israeli airstrikes targeting the Gaza Strip characterized a flare-up of the Israeli–Palestinian conflict in May 2021, which was interrupted by a truce on May 21. On the 6th of May, Palestinians demonstrated in East Jerusalem over the Supreme Court of Israel's expected verdict on the eviction of six Palestinian families from Sheikh Jarrah.

Under international law, the territory, which Israel has essentially annexed, is part of the Palestinian territories that Israel now occupies. The demonstrations swiftly devolved into violent clashes between Jewish and Palestinian demonstrators. On May 7, Israeli forces attacked the al-Aqsa Mosque, Islam's third holiest site, which is located on the Temple Mount, Judaism's holiest place. Stone-throwing Palestinians were met with tear gas, rubber bullets, and stun grenades by police. As a result of the conflict in Israel, Palestinian rockets have murdered 12 people, including one kid (Imseis 2021).

The Israel Defense Forces announced on May 11 that at least 15 of the Palestinians killed were verified Hamas members, as well as that other Palestinian civilians were killed by errant rocket fire within the Gaza Strip (Imseis 2021).

The Palestinian National Authority claimed at least 1,900 Palestinians injured as of May 20, 2021, while Israel claimed at least 200 Israelis injured as of May 12, 2021. At least 72,000 Palestinians had been displaced as of May 19th.

Hamas originally requested a truce on May 13th, but Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu rejected it. On the 18th of May, France, Egypt, and Jordan stated that they had filed a UN Security Council resolution calling for a ceasefire. On May 21, 2021, Israel and Hamas agreed to a truce, following 11 days of war in which both sides claimed victory.

As a result, the peace process has repeatedly stagnated. Despite this, all sides – as well as foreign parties – have sought new conversations on several occasions, demonstrating considerable unhappiness with the existing situation (Imseis 2021).

Solutions to Consider

The Palestinian-Israeli conflict may be solved in two ways. Either option would necessitate significant concessions on both sides. The "one-state solution" would see Israel's land and the Palestinian territories it now controls merged into a single entity. For Israelis, the issue is that the country would no longer be a Jewish state, but rather one with an equal proportion of Palestinian Christians and Muslims. The issue for Palestinians would be ensuring that they had full citizenship rights (McCarthy 1990).

The "two-state solution" would see Israel and Palestine coexisting (comprised of the West Bank and Gaza). Either a partitioning of Jerusalem, shared Israeli-Palestinian rule of the city, or acknowledgement of Jerusalem as an open, international city would be part of this solution. Both parties would have to give up their ambitions to govern the whole region under

a two-state solution. Israel would have to relinquish sovereignty of the occupied territories and remove all of its inhabitants from regions it has conquered since 1967 (Said 1992).

Either option would really be difficult to implement since it would need good leadership from the international community, Israelis, and Palestinians. However, as international crises and human rights violations worsen, failing to find a solution is becoming less of an option. A just and equitable resolution to the dispute would be extremely beneficial to worldwide peace and stability (Irfan 2020).

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